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ENERGIZING LEARNING: EXPLORING HOW ACTION SONGS TRANSFORM CLASSROOM ENGAGEMENT AMONG EDUCATION COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract

This qualitative phenomenological inquiry explored the role of action songs in promoting classroom engagement among educator students at Abuyog Community College. To date, the literature had an identified gap on how action songs were used with higher education students, particularly preservice teachers. The objective of the study was to identify how these new and innovative pedagogical approaches affected student engagement, interest, and educational experiences. Participants in the study consisted of five education students of varying majors (English, Mathematics, Science, Social Studies, Elementary Education) and three instructors that had experience using action songs. The primary form of data collection was through semi-structured interviews and were analysed thematically.

This study is anchored at Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory and Constructivism Learning Theory, theories of embodied cognition and kinaesthetic learning, theories of self-determination, and active learning pedagogy. The study provided valuable contributions to education students, educators, curriculum developers, and future researchers, in a way that encouraged the use of more practical and creative pedagogical approaches. While the study was limited to Abuyog Community College, it also contributed to advancing teaching and learning practices within similar contexts, especially in rural and public college settings in the Philippines.

Keywords: *Action Songs, Classroom Engagement, Education Students, Community, Experiential Learning, Active Learning*

INTRODUCTION

Learning was a fundamental process for students, especially for education students who were preparing to become educators. It allowed them to gain the knowledge, skills, and values needed for their profession. However, learning sometimes became challenging or tedious, particularly when students were not fully engaged during lessons. According to Fredricks, Blumenfeld, and Paris (2004), student engagement was essential because it affected their attention, motivation, and ultimately, their academic success. When students were engaged, they participated more actively and retained information better.

Traditional teaching methods like lectures and note-taking often fail to maintain students' interest and motivation. Psychologist Csikszentmihalyi (1990) introduced the idea of "flow," a state of deep engagement that occurs when learning activities are both enjoyable and challenging. Seeking to create this flow, educators have turned to creative methods like action songs, which combine singing with physical movements linked to the lyrics. Medina (2008) noted that integrating music and movement activates multiple brain areas, improving memory and lesson comprehension. Similarly,

Paquette and Rieg (2008) found that action songs help students stay focused, enhance language development, and boost retention of new information. Thus, action songs serve as an effective, interactive teaching strategy that promotes engagement and learning.

Action songs had been widely used in early childhood and elementary classrooms to teach language skills, numbers, and social behaviours. However, the benefits of action songs were not limited to young learners. According to Hallam (2010), music and movement could also be effective tools for increasing motivation and engagement among older students, including those in higher education.

Despite the many studies showing the positive effects of music and movement on learning, there was still limited research on how action songs impacted the classroom engagement of education students in college settings. Most of the existing studies focused on younger children or informal learning environments, which meant there was a gap in the literature about the use of action songs among college students who were training to become teachers. Understanding how action songs affected this specific group was important because they were the ones applying these techniques in their future classrooms.

This study aimed to fill that gap by exploring the role of action songs in promoting classroom engagement among education students at Abuyog Community College. By using a multiple case study approach, the research examined different groups of students to better understand the experiences, benefits, and challenges related to the use of action songs in their learning process.

The findings of this study provided valuable insights for educators and future teachers. It encouraged the use of more creative teaching methods, such as action songs, to make learning more enjoyable and effective. In addition, the study helped education students recognize the value of incorporating music and movement in their own teaching practices.

Statement of the Problem

This study explored the experiences of educators and groups of education students to better understand how action songs influenced their participation and interest in class activities.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do education students describe their learning experiences using action songs during classroom engagement?
2. How do action songs affect students' participation and interest in class activities across different groups?
3. What are the benefits of using action songs in improving classroom engagement among education students?
4. **What insights does the researcher gain about the use of action songs in education department through conducting this study?**

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a phenomenological inquiry design to explore how action songs influenced classroom engagement among education students at Abuyog Community College. According to Creswell (2013), phenomenology is a qualitative research design in which the researcher “describes the common meaning for several individuals of their lived experiences of a concept or a phenomenon.” In this case, the focus was on understanding the lived experiences of students with action songs in the classroom.

This design supported the study’s goal of gaining deeper insights into the learning experiences of students, which could not be fully captured by quantitative methods alone. By examining the perceptions and experiences of education students, this research provides a broader understanding of how action songs function as a teaching strategy in diverse classroom dynamics and learning contexts at the tertiary level.

Research Instrument

This paper primarily used a semi-structured interview guide as the main research instrument to collect data from both students and instructors. The interview guides were designed with open-ended questions that allowed participants to share their personal experiences and perceptions regarding the use of action songs in their English or education-related classes.

For students, the questions focused on how action songs influenced their engagement, motivation, and participation in the classroom. For instructors, the interviews explored their perspectives on incorporating action songs as a teaching strategy, including how they used the songs during lessons and their observations of students’ responses.

Validation of Research Instrument

For this research, face validity was established by aligning the interview questions with the study’s objectives. The research instructor and mentor reviewed the instruments to ensure that the questions were clear, appropriate, and acceptable for exploring students’ and instructors’ experiences with action songs.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Abuyog Community College, a public tertiary institution located in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines. The college offered several undergraduate education programs, including Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) and Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) programs. The participants in this study were selected education students and instructors from each program using action songs in the class.

Research Participants

This study involved two groups of participants from the College of Education at Abuyog Community College: selected education students and instructors with experience in using action songs in their teaching.

A total of five (5) education students were selected using criterion-based purposive sampling. These participants included one (1) student from each major under the education program: English, Mathematics, Science, Social Studies, and Elementary Education (BEED).

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In addition to the students, three (3) instructors were purposively selected based on their teaching experience and occasional use of action songs in their English or education-related classes. Although action songs were not consistently used in all their lessons, these instructors had previously integrated them into their teaching and were able to reflect on their effects on student engagement. Their participation provided valuable insight into instructional strategies and perspectives from the teaching side.

Data Analysis

The data from the interviews were analysed using thematic analysis, a qualitative method well-suited for phenomenological studies. Researchers transcribed the interviews verbatim, then thoroughly reviewed the transcripts to identify significant statements, themes, and patterns related to action songs' role in student engagement. Coding was done manually or with software to organize the data into meaningful categories. The analysis clustered shared participant experiences while acknowledging individual differences, guided by the study's objectives and research questions to provide a clear, in-depth understanding of how action songs influenced classroom engagement. This systematic approach ensured comprehensive interpretation of the qualitative data.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection began after securing the necessary approvals and informed consent from participants. The researchers scheduled and conducted semi-structured interviews individually with the selected students and instructors at a convenient time and location within the college. Each interview was audio-recorded (with permission) to ensure accurate data capture and later transcription. The researchers also took notes during the interviews to supplement the recordings. The data gathering process took place over several weeks, allowing time for follow-up questions if needed to clarify participants' responses.

Ethical Considerations

This study strictly adhered to ethical standards to protect the rights and welfare of all participants. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from each participant, ensuring they understood the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Participants' privacy and confidentiality were maintained by anonymizing all personal information in the research records and reports. The data collected were used solely for academic purposes.

Researcher Reflexivity

According to McLeod (2024), reflexivity in research involved acknowledging and examining the researcher's biases and assumptions throughout the study. In this research, the team initially assumed that action songs would be universally beneficial to all students. However, participants' varied responses—particularly those indicating that some learners felt shy or uncomfortable—challenged this assumption and emphasized the need for cautious interpretation.

Moreover, the researchers were mindful of potential social desirability bias, where students might have responded positively to please the interviewer. To address this, the researchers ensured anonymity and encouraged honest responses during interviews.

Finally, the researchers themselves as Language and Literature students experience the benefits of doing actions songs to boost learning and classroom engagement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Upon analysing the data, four primary themes were identified through thematic analysis. These themes reflected students' and instructors' actual experiences and perceptions of using action songs during classroom activities. Direct quotes were included to validate their experiences and provide authentic insights.

Action Songs as a Source of Engagement and Enjoyment

This theme highlighted how action songs made learning sessions lively and enjoyable. Participants consistently reported feeling energized and motivated when songs were incorporated into lessons. One respondent shared: Participant No. 1 majoring in Science said "I would describe it nga entertaining I would be more engaging sa mga activities mga sugad or lessons." ("I would describe it as entertaining, and I became more engaged in activities such as lessons.")

Participant 2 (BEED) emphasized its positive effect on mood: emphasized its positive effect on mood: "*Pag na-ay action songs murag ma-energize kita... para sa mga bata ma-entertain maging nindot ang bungad sa atong adlaw.*" ("When there are action songs, it feels like we get energized... for the students, it is entertaining and makes the start of our day better.")

Instructors also observed this effect. One noted: "From my experience, when I use action songs at the start of class, students become more alive. Even those who are usually quiet start smiling and participating. It sets a positive mood and makes them more attentive." (Instructor 1)

Both students and instructors agreed that action songs establish a lively and positive atmosphere, making lessons more enjoyable and engaging.

Boosting Participation and Classroom Interaction

The second theme focuses on how action songs influence student participation and social interaction. For instance, one participant noted: "Action songs increase engagement and interaction with other students. When everyone sings together, the whole class becomes more united and involved."

On the other hand, Participant No.3 confirmed that action songs emphasized behavioral change as he said "It affects my participation specially *parehas saak na dre gud duro nakiki belong to another, nagiging interesting siya saak, na-a awake it akon mind.* Yes, it changes how I usually behave." And this was agreed by Participant 4 an English Major student. Instructor 2 added "Action songs create a shared activity where all students can join in regardless of their skill level. I noticed that students become less shy and more collaborative after we do an action song together."

This demonstrates that action songs act as an equalizer, promoting inclusivity and encouraging even less confident students to join in the activity.

Enhancing Memory and Learning Retention

Several participants acknowledged that action songs serve as mnemonic devices, aiding in memorization. One participant stated:

"*Nakakahinumdom kami sadto san formula... tungod sadto na kanta bagan nakahinumdom giap kami sadto san formula.*" Participant 3 (Math student)

(We were able to remember the formula... because of that song, it seemed that we still recalled the formula.) Another shared a childhood example:

"*Because we sang it repeatedly at the start of class, I was able to retain the parts of the body in my long-term memory.*" Participants 5 (Social Studies)

Instructors echoed this point. One remarked: "When I integrate action songs with academic content, like formulas or grammar patterns, the students remember better. Some even recall past lessons weeks later because the melody and movement stuck with them." (Instructor 3)

These responses affirm that when lesson content is combined with rhythm and movement, it becomes easier for learners to recall, particularly for concepts that require repetition and pattern recognition.

Advantages and Limitations of Action Songs

While participants highlighted numerous benefits, they also acknowledged certain drawbacks. One respondent remarked: "*There are many advantages... they make the class more engaging... However, I think action songs are not suitable for all learners... For shy students... action songs might make them hesitant to participate.*" Participant 5 (Social Studies) said. Another pointed out: "*Mas applicable and suitable pero iba-iba kasi an mga learners so meda iba Dre suitable meda kita gn sesering na multiple intelligences.*" Participant 1 (Science) ("Action songs are generally applicable and suitable, but since learners differ, they may not work equally for everyone." This reflects the idea of multiple intelligences.")

Instructors also recognized this challenge, as Instructor 1 explained "Not all students are comfortable with singing or moving, especially at the college level. Some think it is childish at first. But once they see its purpose, most of them join in. The key is using action songs at the right time, not overdoing them."

This indicates that while action songs can be a powerful strategy, they must be adapted to different learning styles to avoid excluding students who are less comfortable with singing or movement.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Both students and instructors recognized the significant role of action songs in enhancing classroom engagement among education students at Abuyog Community College.
2. Action songs encouraged active participation, boosted attentiveness, improved memory retention, and fostered a collaborative classroom atmosphere.
3. Instructors confirmed that action songs set a positive tone for lessons and helped unify students, while also supporting long-term retention of academic content. However, findings revealed that action songs were not equally effective for all learners, as some students—particularly those who were shy or self-conscious—were hesitant to participate. This highlighted the importance of adapting the strategy to diverse learning needs and using it appropriately within the classroom setting.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

The following actions are recommended:

1. It was recommended that instructors integrate action songs strategically in classroom activities, particularly during motivation, review, and transition phases, while providing alternative approaches for learners who might have felt uncomfortable with singing or movement.

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2. Teacher training programs and curriculum developers were encouraged to include music- and movement-based strategies in professional development to support learner-centered and inclusive pedagogy.
3. Future teachers are encouraged to explore action songs as part of their teaching toolkit, adjusting them according to student diversity and classroom context.
4. Future researchers are advised to replicate or expand this study in other institutions, subjects, and cultural settings to for varied results.

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